

The polarization switching in nanoscale with an anisotropic 2D magnetic semiconductor

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ABSTRACT

Here we present a proof-of-concept device demonstrating the feasibility to control the light polarization using the properties of the magnetic 2D materials. The studied structure consists of a diluted magnetic semiconductor quantum well and a thin layer of CrSBr. We show that by application of the external field we can switch the sign of the polarization of the emitted light. The theoretical modeling confirms that such a switching is a direct consequence of a colossal shift of the exciton lines observed in the high energy range of the CrSBr spectra. Owing to this mechanism, the full rotation of the polarization state can be realized in a layer as thin as few hundred nanometers.

1. Introduction

Control of the polarization of light is one of the core ingredients in almost all advanced optical applications. A well established toolbox used in optical laboratories includes elements such as polarizers, waveplate retarders, but also dynamically controlled polarization modulators [1]. Typically, such modulators rely on the changes induced in the refractive index of the given material by application of either electric or magnetic field.

Additional challenges emerge when working in micro-scale, e.g., to achieve deep in-situ modulation of the polarization state of the light emitted from low dimensional quantum emitters. Switching of polarization over the sub-micrometre distance requires materials with exceptionally strong coupling between its optical properties and either magnetic or electric field [2]. In this respect, novel 2D materials can open new possibilities [3]. Such layered materials can be transferred onto various nanostructures without the need of lattice matching, and a wide variety of already identified 2D materials include some with exceptionally good optical properties. A lot of experimental effort was put in the electrical gating of such structures, leading to showcasing a number of electrically-controlled devices [4–10], possibly due to much narrower field of use due to inherent limitation in local application of the magnetic field.

In this work we present a proof-of-concept of such application using a magnetic 2D layered semiconductor – chromium sulfide bromide (CrSBr) in which the optical spectrum can be tuned with the

external magnetic field [11–13]. With a unique coupling between electronic structure and magnetic ordering, one can tune the energy of the excitons in CrSBr over the range of over 100 meV with the external magnetic field as low as 2 T [14]. Importantly, due to strongly anisotropic character of CrSBr, the associated change in the index of refraction of CrSBr can be used to alter the polarization of the transmitted light.

Our proof-of-concept structure consists of a quantum well (QW) made of Diluted Magnetic Semiconductor (DMS) with a multi-layer CrSBr exfoliated onto its surface, which we subject to an out-of-plane external magnetic field, as depicted in Fig. 1. The principal role of the QW is to emit light with well defined polarization state ($\sigma+$ or $\sigma-$, depending on the sign of the external magnetic field [15]). The function of the CrSBr layer is to alter this polarization state, switching it into linear polarization, depending on the value of the applied field.

It is important to note a distinct difference between classical magneto-optical modulators and the proposed structure. A typical application involving magneto-optical effects is the Faraday rotator, which involves magnetic field along the optical axis. Magnetic field is also known to induce a linear birefringence via Cotton–Mouton effect, but only in transverse geometry with external magnetic field perpendicular to the optical axis. In contrast, CrSBr features a strong triaxial structural anisotropy that dictates the optical selection rules that only the light

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Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the structure discussed in this work. Structure below the CrSBr flakes denote the semimagnetic quantum well with substrate. With crimson arrow was marked the direction, in which magnetic field (B) was applied. (b) Optical microscope image of the CrSBr flake chosen in the experiment. With arrows were marked the in-plane crystallographic axes. Spots, in which measurements on-flake and near-flake were conducted are marked with full and empty circles respectively. (c) Example polarization-resolved differential reflectance of CrSBr (with respect to the signal reflected from the substrate) in the energy range of higher-energy excitons in zero external magnetic field. The lines represent polarizations set along in-plane a -/ b -axis (\hat{a}/\hat{b}), showing a dispersion driven by an exciton strongly polarized along b -axis (noted as Ω_3).

polarized along b crystallographic axis couples with optical transitions in NIR-VIS region, even in moderate-to-strong magnetic fields [11,16]. As a result, in the case of CrSBr the primary magneto-optical effect is linear birefringence even if the external magnetic field is oriented along the optical axis of our structure.

Another advantage of CrSBr is that its electronic structure hardly depends on the number of layers [17]. While interesting phenomena like spin-flip transitions and surface excitons can be observed in few-layered flakes [11,18], these effects are negligible for thicker flakes. In result, we are able to use a wide range of thicknesses, which is profitable for finding optimal flake thickness for a device. The same could not be achieved with TMDs, popularly used in devices, as a direct optical transition is only available in monolayers.

2. Experimental details

CrSBr monocrystals were exfoliated mechanically on the surface of the MBE-grown nanostructure with a single 10 nm $\text{Cd}_{0.96}\text{Mn}_{0.04}\text{Te}$ quantum well, serving as an emitter. The barriers of the QW are $(\text{Cd,Mg})\text{Te}$ 50 nm layers, with 34% of magnesium content. The concentration of the manganese in the QW layer was chosen to ensure a complete circular polarization of the emitted light under our experimental conditions. During the process of exfoliation additional heating of the sample on hotplate was used, to ensure better adhesion of the CrSBr layers to the surface. It allowed for covering much larger surface area with the exfoliated material. That is especially notable as we found out that CrSBr has low adhesion to the surface of $(\text{Cd,Mg})\text{Te}$.

The sample was submerged in liquid helium (1.8 K) in the optical cryostat along with the aspheric lens mounted on piezoelectric stages allowing collecting optical signal from the micrometer spot size ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$). All measurements were performed with 661 nm semiconductor laser, which power was reduced with optical filters to 50 μW .

3. Results and discussion

As described in the [Experimental details](#) section, the role of the emitter in this experiment was played by a single $(\text{Cd,Mn})\text{Te}$ QW, with $(\text{Cd,Mg})\text{Te}$ barriers, that emits in the energy of 1.7 eV. In the external magnetic field in Faraday configuration, the DMS QW experiences a giant Zeeman shift [15,19]. At the temperature $T = 1.8\text{K}$ this shift reaches about 20 meV in magnetic fields up to 3 T. This shift by itself is not crucial for the current study, but we exploit the fact that due to thermalization between splitted spin states the emitted light

Fig. 2. Pseudo-color map of magneto-PL from uncovered QW (from the spot marked in Fig. 1(b) by empty circles) in σ^+ circular polarization. Note the lack of PL signal in negative magnetic fields, which evidences that the emitted light is fully circularly polarized, except the transition point at $B = 0\text{T}$.

is circularly polarized σ^\pm . It is evidenced by the map presented in Fig. 2a, which shows that the σ^+ emission occurs exclusively at positive magnetic fields — or equivalently, that the photoluminescence at $B > 0$ is polarized purely σ^+ .

The situation vastly changes if this emitted light goes through a thin (210 nm) layer of CrSBr. Experimentally, the two compared situations corresponded to the spots less than 200 μm apart, as shown in Fig. 1b, which allows us to confidently attribute all the observed differences to the effect of the additional CrSBr layer.

As discussed earlier, CrSBr has a strong in-plane anisotropy linked to the crystallographic directions a and b [11,16]. As a consequence, we expect difference in the phase shift experienced by the transmitted light polarized along those axes, referred to as π_a and π_b polarizations. Polarization-resolved differential reflectance spectra are presented in Fig. 1c, showcasing the exciton contribution in polarization π_b , which was marked with \hat{b} on the graph. This dispersion can be contributed to exciton Ω_3 more thoroughly described in Ref. [14]. One clear contribution to this difference stems from the fact that nearby excitonic absorption has electric dipole moment along the b axis, which entails a respective change in the relevant index of refraction, according to the Kramers–Kronig relations [20]. As the absolute measurement of the phase shift of π_a and π_b is challenging, instead, we measured the photoluminescence signal in diagonal polarizations (denoted as π_{a+b} and π_{a-b}). The results of such measurements are shown in Figs. 3a and 3b.

Both of the signals measured in linear polarizations (Figs. 3a and 3b) feature significant variation in intensity as a function of magnetic field. Under a weak field ($B \lesssim 0.5\text{T}$), the emitted light has clear excess of π_{a+b} polarization over π_{a-b} polarization. It can be easily interpreted assuming that the birefringent CrSBr crystal acts as waveplate retarder with retardation close to $\pi/2$. However, upon increasing the magnetic field this relation become reversed and at $B = 2.5\text{T}$ the dominant polarization of the two is the π_{a-b} component. We stress that such changes cannot be related to the QW, as it maintains a stable σ^+ polarization of emission (compare Fig. 2), which has equal contribution of any linear polarization. The only possible cause of switching from π_{a+b} to π_{a-b} polarization upon changing value of the magnetic field are therefore changes of birefringence of the CrSBr layer.

Interestingly, the switching between π_{a+b} to π_{a-b} polarization discussed in the previous paragraph occurs quite suddenly at field close to 1.5 T. The abruptness of this change can be appreciated in Fig. 4(b), which presents the diagonal polarization Stokes parameter $V = \frac{I_{a+b} - I_{a-b}}{I_{a+b} + I_{a-b}}$, where I_j is intensity of PL spectrum in polarization π_j at the energy of 1695 meV. The abrupt switching of the polarization must be related to steep change in the index of refraction as a function of the external magnetic field, which in turn can be linked with presence of a recently recognized higher-band excitons experiencing a giant shift of 100 meV in magnetic field up to 2 T [14].

In order to further verify our interpretation we have performed a simulation based on transfer matrix method. The CrSBr was modeled as

Fig. 3. (a) and (b) Pseudo-color map of magneto-PL from QW covered with CrSBr (from the spot marked in Fig. 1(b) by filled circles) in two, orthogonal diagonal polarizations $\pi_{\pm 45}$. Notable is the switching in signal strength between polarizations around $B = 1.5$ T. (c) Reference scan of magneto-PL from uncovered QW (empty circle in Fig. 1(b)) in linear polarization along flake axis with excitonic dielectric function.

Fig. 4. (a) Intensity of the QW PL for polarization π_b with a clear dip marking the crossing of the excitonic absorption through the QW emission line. (b) Experimentally observed switching of the polarization expressed in terms of the diagonal polarization Stokes parameter. (c) Simulation of the observed behavior according to the described model of Lorenz oscillators corresponding to the excitons with energy affected by the magnetic field.

a dielectric slab with thickness of $d = 210$ nm with an anisotropic dielectric function. Consistently with the approach used by Wang et al. [21], we used a parametrization of the dielectric function of CrSBr by a series of Lorentz oscillators

$$\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \sum \frac{f}{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2 - i\gamma\omega}. \quad (1)$$

Within this framework, the birefringence of the considered CrSBr layer has two contributions: (1) the baseline ϵ_∞ is different for a - and b -polarized light and (2) different set of oscillators are relevant for the two polarizations, accordingly with the optical selection rules. In fact, since all excitonic transitions observed in the VIS-IR range of the spectrum are linearly polarized along the b -axis, the model dielectric function for a -polarized light has a constant value of $\epsilon_\infty^{(a)} = 10$, as in Ref. [21]. For the sake of simplicity, the parameters of the Lorenz oscillators in the b -polarized light were also taken directly from Ref. [21]. However, since the earlier works were focused on the spectral range around 1.3 eV, the oscillators in Ref. [21] included only the fundamental exciton transitions occurring in that range. In order to account for a higher band exciton [14], which are crucial for understanding of the switching effect discussed in this work, we have added an additional oscillator with phenomenological value of the amplitude of $\hbar^2 f = 0.286 \text{ eV}^2$ and damping of $\hbar\gamma = 55 \text{ meV}$. Compared to the parameters given by Ref. [21], We have also introduced a minor adjustment to the value of the $\epsilon_\infty^{(b)} = 13.2$ to improve agreement with the experiment in the spectral range analyzed here. Similarly, due to different experimental conditions (different temperature, excitation conditions and properties of the substrate under CrSBr), the zero-field exciton energy included in our simulation was treated as a free parameter. Including other excitons neglected so far, such as Ω_4 exciton discussed in Ref. [14], would possibly improve the results of our simulation even further, but here we restrict ourselves to the minimal viable model for the sake of clarity.

The core mechanism of the model is that the frequencies of the considered Lorenz oscillators depend on the external magnetic field. Particularly important is the shift of the higher energy exciton $\Delta\omega(B)$, which is discussed in details in Ref. [14]. At zero magnetic field, the exciton is on the higher-energy side of the signal of interest at $E \approx 1.70 \text{ eV}$. Within a Lorenz oscillator model, the presence of such an excitonic resonance reduces the effective index of refraction for b -polarization and — as a consequence — the birefringence of the layer. Upon increasing external magnetic field, the exciton experiences a strong red-shift, crossing the QW line near the field of $B = 1.5 \text{ T}$ (see Fig. 4(a)). For higher magnetic fields, the exciton stays on the lower-energy side of the probing QW emission and thus the presence of the excitonic resonance increases the birefringence of the CrSBr layer. The simulated variation of the diagonal Stokes parameter is shown in Fig. 4(c). Expressed in terms of wave retardation, the results of our simulation give us -0.087λ at $B = 0.6 \text{ T}$ and $+0.031\lambda$ at $B = 2.0 \text{ T}$.

All the results serve as a proof of concept that such a micro-scale retarder can be constructed. The effectiveness of the device could be further enhanced with precise selection of flake thickness, as the flake used in the experiment was chosen randomly.

Operation of such a device depends also on the wavelength of interest. The showcased structure utilized a (Cd,Mn)Te/(Cd,Mg)Te as a light emitter, which anchored our experiments at $\lambda \approx 730 \text{ nm}$. Such a case fulfills an important condition that neither at low nor at high magnetic fields does the exciton line overlap with the wavelength of interest. Fulfilling this condition assures that both before and after the switch, the absorption is minimized. From that perspective the large excitonic shift of CrSBr [14] is particularly beneficial, since it defines the spectral window for viable operation of such structures.

4. Summary

We have created a proof-of-concept controllable micro-scale retarder with a nanoscale emitter and an anisotropic 2D material with strong magneto-optical coupling. Process of constructing such device having an emitter is an easy and fast process as it only consists of mechanical exfoliation of CrSBr flakes on the surface of the emitter. On a randomly chosen flake as thin as 210 nm, we reached switching diagonal polarization degree from -0.50 to $+0.2$ by changing magnetic field from 0.6 T to 2.0 T. The performance of this particular structure could be further improved by precise selection of the flake thickness, but it is a clear demonstration of new unexplored potential unlocked by magnetic 2D materials which feature strong coupling between its magnetic ordering and optical properties.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

R. Komar: Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis. **A. Łopion:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Formal analysis. **K. Mosina:** Resources. **A. Söll:** Resources. **Z. Sofer:** Resources. **W. Pacuski:** Resources. **C. Faugeras:** Resources. **P. Kossacki:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **T. Kazimierczuk:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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